

FAAM facility for airborne atmospheric measurements

FLIGHT FOLDER

Flight No.: B305
Date: 11 July 2007
Take Off 09:26:17
Landing: 13:14:30
Flight Time 3h48m13s

Campaign: COPS

Operating Area: Baden-Baden, Germany

POB	Position	Name	Institute
1	Captain	Al Roberts	Directflight
2	Co-pilot	Ian Ramsay-Rae	Directflight
3	CCM	Gaynor Ottaway	Directflight
4	Mission Scientist 1	Phil Brown	Met Office
5	Mission Scientist 2	Alan Blyth	UFAM
6	Flight Manager	Steve Devereau	FAAM
7	Cloud Physics	Jamie Trembath	FAAM
8	Core Chemistry / CCM2	Stuart Heath	FAAM
9	VACC 1	Barbara Brookes	Leeds University
10	VACC 2	Angela Dean	Leeds University
11	CPI 1	James Dorsey	University of Manchester
12	CPI 2	Hazel Jones	University of Manchester
13	CVI	Jeff Brown	Met Office
14	Nephelometers	Andy Wilson	Met Office
15	Mission Scientist 3	Victoria Smith	Leeds University
16			
17			
18			
19			
20			

Flight Track:

B305 Track 11-JUL-07

FLIGHT SUMMARY

Flight No B305
 Date: 11th July 2007
 Project: COPS
 Location: Baden-Baden

Start Time	End Time	Event	Height (s)	Hdg	Comments
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090823		event	0.33 kft	154	INU to Nav
092109		event	0.33 kft	154	start taxi
092617		T/O	0.32 kft	212	
092927		event	5.9 kft	154	LBBR retract
093006		event	6.0 kft	086	Nevzorov zero
093036		event	6.0 kft	053	J-W zero
093951	095039	Run 1.1	2.7 kft	219	
094107		event	2.7 kft	202	Heimann cal
095231	100132	Run 1.2	2.8 - 2.7 kft	345	
095425		event	2.7 kft	022	J-W, Nevzorov zero
100435		event	9.4 kft	140	PSAP pump off
100716		event	12.0 kft	140	J-W, Nevzorov zero
100755		event	12.0 kft	139	Heimann cal
103208		event	12.0 kft	273	Heimann cal
105035	105319	Run 2.1	10.3 kft	031	
105150		event	10.3 kft	033	Nev zero
105207		event	10.3 kft	032	JW zero
105730	110221	Run 3.1	11.0 - 11.2 kft	206	
110219		event	11.2 kft	127	FFC window iced
110428	111035	Run 4.1	11.9 kft	278	
111249		event	12.0 kft	294	J-W, Nevzorov zero
111313	111513	Run 4.2	12.0 kft	258	
111612	111821	Run 4.3	11.9 - 12.0 kft	357	
112206	112446	Run 4.4	12.0 kft	225	
112400		event	12.0 kft	000	112400 evidence of turbulence probe freezing
112807	113030	Run 4.5	12.0 kft	030	
113404	113605	Run 4.6	12.0 kft	209	
113906	114216	Run 4.7	12.0 kft	342	
113939		event	12.0 kft	342	J-W, Nevzorov zero
115749	115918	Run 5.1	11.0 kft	254	
115915		event	11.0 kft	254	J-W, Nevzorov zero
120248	120317	Run 5.2	11.0 kft	074	
120336	120532	Run 6.1	10.4 - 10.3 kft	075	
120853	121211	Run 6.2	10.3 kft	256	
120959		event	10.3 kft	248	J-W, Nevzorov zero
121454		event	10.3 kft	151	J-W, Nevzorov zero
121517	121651	Run 6.3	10.3 - 10.4 kft	169	
121917	122030	Run 6.4	10.3 kft	274	
122209		event	10.3 kft	290	Heimann cal
122350	122611	Run 6.5	10.3 kft	098	
125144	125352	Profile 1	10.0 - 12.0 kft	172	
125411	125646	Profile 1	12.0 - 15.0 kft	197	
125818	130846	Profile 2	15.1 - 4.1 kft	349	
131430		Land	0.34 kft	213	
131930		shutdown	0.35 kft	160	48 46.91N 8 05.35E

B305 Track 11-JUL-07

EDSB -> EDDS - Overview

NavData Cycle 2007-7 Expires: Thursday, 02 August 2007.

Scale: 1:426851 (1 inch = 5.85 naut mi). Printed on 16 Jul 2007

JEPPESEN

FliteStar 9.2.0.2

PROJECT BRIEF: COPS - Convective and Orographically-induced Precipitation Study.

Scientific Aims: The goal of UK-COPS is to determine the properties of the aerosols that will likely be ingested into the convective clouds that form over the Black Forest mountains and to understand the formation and growth of ice and precipitation in these clouds . We wish to examine:

- the properties of the representative aerosol particles in the clear air that are transported into the convective clouds
- the concentration and size of cloud droplets just above cloud base
- the formation of the first ice due to primary nucleation on ice nuclei (IN)
- the development of ice via secondary processes such as the Hallett-Mossop process, in which new ice particles are generated during the riming growth of ice particles
- other secondary ice production processes, such as evaporative break-up;
- the production of supercooled raindrops and their role in the glaciation process
- the dependence of these processes on the dynamics of the cloud
- the production of precipitation

There will either be 2 flights per day: one in clear air to measure the properties of the aerosols and one later in the convective clouds; or the two parts will be flown in a single flight. Measurements will be made in cumulus clouds when their tops are about 0°C through to when the tops have grown to about -20°C.

Weather conditions:

Developing showers over the Black Forest mountains, Germany, within Box A and probably B.

Safety: Regions that paint RED on the aircraft weather radar should be avoided. No flight into clouds known to be producing lightning. There may be coordination with the DO-128 in Boxes A and B. Other aircraft may also operate in the Rhine Valley.

Key instruments and their operation:

Basic meteorology

- Rosemount temperatures, GE hygrometer
- FWVS
- GPS, INU, turbulence probe When in supercooled liquid water, Flight Manager or PIs should monitor turbulence probe calibrated differential pressures for signs of icing (cessation of variability on signal).

Cloud Physics/Aerosol

- FFSSP, 2DC, 2DP, PCASP, CDP, CIP, SID-1 and SID-2. Normal monitoring to ensure correct operation. Operator should note particular features of interest eg. high concentrations, appearance of pristine ice crystal habits, appearance of large drops ($d > 100 \mu\text{m}$) in 2D imagery when above freezing level.
- CPI as above
- CCN measurements should be made by filling the alleviator whilst in clear air runs.
- J-W LWC and Nevzorov LWC/TWC. Where straight/level and in clear air, these should be zeroed/calibrated and a note made in the Flight Managers log.
- TWC - profile ascents/descents should avoid cloud if possible
- AMS -
- CVI - below cloud base, normal operation is in aerosol mode; above cloud base, normal operation is in CVI mode
- VACC -

Sortie Brief: COPS – Convective and Orographically-induced Precipitation Study
Flight Number: B305
Date: 11 July 2007
Mission Scientists: Phil Brown and Alan Blyth
TO Time: 11:00 local

Sortie Aims: To measure properties of aerosols in the clear air and the development of convective clouds.

Sortie Location: Clear air in Rhine Valley and in convective clouds over Black Forest mountains.

Sortie Summary:

1. Characterise properties of aerosols in clear air at low levels.
2. Penetrate cumulus clouds preferably near the top of the cloud in the updraught. All cloud penetrations should be with *wings level*. Two principal options are:
 - A stationary cloud or system of clouds;
 - B several cumulus clouds either in area (low wind) or passing through the area;
3. Characterise properties of aerosols in detrainment layers around cloud.

Sortie Detail:

1. Out-of-Cloud: All changes in altitude at standard rates (1000 ft/min).
 - 1.1 Take off and climb to FL60 and fly to Z.
 - 1.2 Descend to FL40; Leg Z-X via W almost overpassing Hornisgrinde.
 - 1.3 Leg X-V at FL40
 - 1.4 Leg V-D5 at FL40
 - 1.5 Descend to FL20: Leg D5-D1 via U
 - 1.6 Ascend to FL40: Leg D1-E5 via E1 and T

2. Cloud work:

Note an important feature is to ascend with tops. This requires a non-standard ascent as fast as possible

Option A: Isolated developing clouds – ascend with the clouds near their top. All penetrations at constant altitude.

- A.1 Proceed to 200 m above cloud base.
- A.2 Proceed to about 0°C or top of cloud.
- A.3 Adjust altitude to about 1000 ft below cloud top and penetrate cloud. The penetration should be made at a constant azimuth and altitude if possible. It is important to penetrate the growing turret in the updraught region. A few seconds after clearing cloud, turn and ascend for return to same region of cloud as quickly as possible using procedure turn.
- A.4 Repeat A.3, ascending with the top (if appropriate) at the end of each penetration out of cloud, until FL200 or FL240, or cloud becomes too developed.
- A.5 Repeat A.1 - A.5 for a new developing cumulus, go to **Option B**, or exit box.

Option B: Many developing cumulus clouds – sample many clouds.

- B.1 Proceed to 200 m above cloud base.
- B.2 Proceed to 0°C
- B.3 Commence 10 min runs (turning where appropriate) in along shear direction. Adjust track to randomly sample the updraught regions of growing turrets.

B.4 Ascend to -5°C (i.e. approximately 3500 ft) and repeat above for 10 min.

B.5 Repeat for -10°C , -15°C and -20°C if possible.

3. Detrainment layers

Proceed to level where cloud is being detrained from cloud and either make penetrations or circle around the cloud.

Flight B305

11/07/2007

Mission Scientist Debrief:

Phil Brown

1. Flight Patterns

Take-off from Baden-Karlsruhe (FKB) and ascend to 6000ft initially. Cloudbase at 2900ft at N end of Rhine Valley region. Descent to 2800ft on QNH.

Southbound leg at 2800ft, starting below cloudbase by ~200ft. Toward s the S end of the leg cloudbase lowered beneath flight level and some rain showers appeared. Small turns to avoid both of these. Turn about and repeat the same leg northbound. PCASP gradient in concentration along the valley, higher in the north (800cm⁻³).

Ascend towards the east into the allocated box (A/B), climbing initially to FL120. Stable layer top at around 9500ft, with some convective tops ascending a bit above this level, although mostly outside the boundary of the area initially. Spent around 40 minutes circulating roughly around the perimeter of the box, searching for suitable clouds.

105035 began a leg at 10300ft aiming to penetrate two cloud cells. Further leg following this at 11000ft, T ~ -6C. Estimate ~1500ft below cloud top on this leg. Further leg at 12000ft, but aiming for a different cloud. Quite hard to recognize individual cells when they only penetrate a short range above the stable layer. 4 further legs at 12000ft penetrating various cells, sometimes already in a state of subsiding back into the stable layer. LWC typically 1-1.3 g m⁻³. Radar echoes mainly green, some yellow. Precipitation particles appear to be predominantly supercooled drops at this stage. T ~ -8C and Td ~ -20C in the cloud free environment.

~115800 cloud penetration at 11000ft, T ~ -5.3 with ice particles seen. On repositioning for further penetration, cloud top subsided so descend to 10300ft T ~ -4.2C. Ice needles. During turns following this leg, occasional penetrations of the stratiform cloud top, where this is perturbed upwards by convective activity. 4 further legs at 10300 feet aiming to sample these upper regions of the stratiform cloud. Apparently more ice crystals observed during these legs than earlier in the flight, although CPI images mostly of droplets. 2DC concentrations quite low (~few to 10s l⁻¹) so suspect mostly the result of primary nucleation.

At the end of these legs, it was apparent that convection was even more suppressed and confined below the stable layer than earlier in the flight. Hence, profile ascent FL100, followed by profile descent FL150-4000ft in order to document the inversion structure.

2. Meteorological conditions

Upper trough moving eastwards over the COPS area, with cool west to NW flow over the region. Generally, ~4/8 Cu with base ~ 2900ft over the Rhine Valley but widespread across the entire region. Stable layer at 9500-10000ft, just sufficient to inhibit any deep convection development. Through most of the flight period, ~ 6-7/8 of altostratus in this stable layer. Presume that this was enough to inhibit surface heating and hence any deeper convection development.

Mission Scientist's Log

Flight No **B**.....305 Date ..11/7/07 NameP. Brown Page1 of 4

GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
0925					t/o FKB.
/		2500			below base. (1013).
/		2900			base.
0929		6000			Positioning to descend for run 1.
/					stable layer with ~ 7/8 Stratiform ~ 1000 above this level.
/					4/8 Cu at the 2900 base stratiform cloud obscures the view towards cloud base.
093952		2800			Start R1.1 below base by ~ 200-300 ft.
0945		"			Just above Strasbourg.
0948		"			cloud bases slightly lower in S.
/					wet neph not v. hygroscopic.
095039		"			End Run 1.1. avoiding rain
095231		"			Start R1.2 cloudbase just below level at the start, avoiding cloud
/					Passes cones lower at S end.
1001		"			Approaching W end of run. reduced stratiform cloud around the Cu tops
/		"			End run 1.2 turn R 2 climb.
/		7900			into cloud during climb, brief.
/		9500			Above the stable layer.
/		12000			Some deeper clouds punching further to S outside area.
101330					2 photos, clouds just outside area

Mission Scientist's Log

Flight No **B.305** Date 11/7/07 Name Page 2 of 4

GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
1016		12000			SID 2 problems, random firing or lost connection.
1031		"			Coming down to SW corner of box
/					~ 7/8 As below, with Cu tops just penetrating by a few 100 ft.
105035		10250			Start Run 2.2 cloud tops to penetrate.
105225		"			into cloud 2
					End run. 2.1
-		11000			T -6.0 Td -13.5
105728		"			Start run. 3.1 aiming for its a bit away, in corner of area so manoeuvre for it.
/		/			will sample more along wind.
/		"			~ 1500 below top?
/					End run & climb turn.
		12000			T -7.7 Td -20.3
/					Start run, heading for wrong cloud.
					turn left to pick up original.
110807					into cloud, top few 100 above
/					hwc ~ 1 gm ⁻³
		12000	258		repeat leg., slightly off wind. 7ms/283
					Cloud top lower.
111427		"			in cloud.
					End 4.2
111612		"	356		Start 4.3 crosswind.
					top ~ few 100 above.

111720

in cloud, exited in turn.

Mission Scientist's Log

Flight No **B** 305 Date 11/7/07 Name Page 3 of 4

GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
112120		12000			in turn for another run through last cloud.
112206					R 4.4
112347		"			ix.
					End 4.4 T-8.5 Td-20.7
112807		"			Start 4.5 painting green on radar
					~ 200 below top,
112940					in cloud. move downward
—					in that pass, consistent with cloud top shrinking
113530					just clipped cloud top,
113605		"			End 4.6 hvc was much lower
		11000	254		T-5.3 Td-17.5
					Start run. wind still 11/270°
1158					into cloud. ice particles.
115918		"			End 5.1 hvc ~ 1 gm ⁻³
		10200			Start 5.2 dropped down
					T-4.2 needles.
1206		"			skimming cloud tops during turn
—					
120853		10300			Start run 6.2, -5.3
—					in the stratiform tops. overshooting only a few 100 ft.
121010					in cloud. out after few sec.
—					Nhvc didn't return to zero after last cloud.
121517		10300			Start 6.3 -3.9
121600					in cloud, top ~ 11000

pass 4 ms⁻¹ updraft.

Mission Scientist's Log

Flight No **B** 305 Date 11/7/07 Name Page 4 of 4

GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
					Start Turn 6.4.
121930					in cloud, weaker updraft stronger down.
122030					End 6.4, repeat altitude.
—					200 only a few/L'
		10300			Start 6.5
122507					in cloud. - few sec. huc low
1234					at W edge of area. Good cells are still upstream, go descend to 10000 for a run in stratiform top.
123545					in cloud.
123925		10000			in cloud.
124045					" " , Sc tops rising as we go S.
—					clouds now more suppressed than at the start.
125144		10000	178		Start P1
		15000			End P1 moist layer here.
1256					
1258		15000			Start P2 few turns.
		7000			1000 ft/min down to here.
—		5200			nice vigorous rain showers here.
130846		4000			End P2
					debrief. 1600 local.

Debrief items.

1. Confirm Ntwc oper. T 70°C for this flight. Request 90°C future

CLOUD PHYSICS LOG Flight B305

Date: 11/07/07	Operator: jt	DRS Time: +0	AU1 Time: +0	DAU2 Time: -2	DAU3 Time: +0	Aux1 Time: +0	Aux2 Time: +0	Page 1 of 1
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G.M.T	PCASP		FFSSP	SID1	SID2	2D2-C		2D2-P		CIP25			CIP100			Habit	Remarks
	Conc/cc	Mean R	Block TX	Count	Count	Conc/L	Max size	Conc/m3	Max size	Conc m3	Max size	LWC	Conc m3	Max size	LWC		
09:39:51	800	0.08	36	3	0	0	0	0	0						0	Start run 1.1	
09:41:00	500	0.08	36	3	0	0	0	0	0						0		
09:43:00	450	0.08	36														
09:45:00	464	0.08	37	3	0	0	0	0	0						0		
09:47:00	535	0.08	37	3	0	0	0	0	0						0		
09:49:00	320	0.08	37	3	0	0	0	0	0						0		
09:50:38	226	0.08	37	10	10	10	600								1	End run 1.1	
09:52:31	253	0.08	37	3	0	0	0	0	0						0	Start run 1.2	
09:54:00	380	0.08	37	3	0	0	0	0	0								
09:56:00	514	0.08	37	3	0	0	0	0	0								
09:58:00	523	0.08	37	3	0	0.5	800	0	0						1		
10:01:31	552	0.08	38	3	0	0	0	0	0						0	End of run 1.2	
10:14:00																SID2 strange data for approx 5-7 mins SID2 keeps getting unrecognised meages	
10:20:30																SID2 False counts SID2 10:22:25 M6x error SID2 10:23:18 Unrecognised message (#22) it becomes SID stopped responding Lazer power 12mW detector 9.3kV	
10:31:32					1000								-8 amb	12000ft		Phantom SI temps cont = 15 fgpa = 18 pod =15 Hd heater = 9 hd amb = 1 laser = 13 det = 18	
10:50:53	1000	0.1	125	3000		5	600								1	1 st cloud pass run 2.1	
10:52:45	1000	0.1	203	5005		5	600	900	600						1	2 nd cloud pass possible columns as well	
11:01:35	10000	0.16	280	7000		10	225	1650							1	3 rd cloud pass run 3.1 possible small ice	
11:08:16	10000	0.16	336	7000		25	475	725	1000						10/1	4 th cloud pass run 4.1 large ice in 2cd	
11:14:30	10000	0.16	285	7000		100	350	2125	1000						1	5 th pass run 4.2 large ice ?	
11:17:50	6000	0.16	503	7000		15	400	116							1	6 th pass run 4.3	
11:23:51	4560	0.1	620	7000		15	350	750							1	7 th pass run 4.4	
11:29:43	8000	0.16	676	8000		30	600								1	8 th pass run 4.5	
11:35:23	5000	0.14	690	8000		50	200								1/10	9 th pass run 4.6	
11:58:30	2000	0.12	714	8000		700	600								8	10 th pass run 5	
12:03:50	3000	0.1	780	8000		500	800								8	11 th pass run 5.1 lot of needles	
12:08:45	4.5	0.13	1100	8000		75	700	12150							6	12 pass run 6.2	
12:11:12	2.2	0.1	1137	8000		10	300								8	13 th pass and 12 th pass long time	
12:16:03	2.2	0.09	1212	8000		12	400	450							8	14 th pass run 6.3	
12:19:33	51	0.12	1316	8000		15	450								8	15 th pass run 6.4, needles obvious	
12:25:08	240	0.12	1337	8000		1	200								1/6	16 th pass run 6.5	
12:40:58	250	0.2	1519	8000		10	60								6	17 th pass	

CLOUD PHYSICS PROCESSING LOG

Flight number: B305 **T/O:** 09:26:17
Date of flight: 11/07/07 **Land:** 13:14:30

A) FFSSP PROCESSING		
Processing Stage	Done?	Comments
1) Transfer *.txt files from DVD to processing PC Bnnn_FFSSP_hh.txt for each hour of data Bnnn_FFSSP_HVMS.txt	NO	hh = Last sec processed =
2) FTP the files (ascii) from the PC to directory PMSDATA: on FLOODS		File size =
3) FLOODS> RUN MRFB:[PMS.FAST_FFSSP]FFSSP_EXTRACT_TAS a) Flight number: Bnnn b) Path name: MFDDATA:Bnnn_MFDX c) Output directory: PMSDATA: d) Start time: <i>0 if unknown (see comment box)</i> e) End time: <i>240000 if unknown</i>		Use time just before/after take-off/landing. If T/O /landing just after/before the hour, ensure start/end time is before/after the hour if there is an FFSSP_hh.txt file for that hour.
4) FLOODS> RUN MRFB:[PMS.FAST_FFSSP]FFSSP_PROCESS_TXT a) Flight number: Bnnn b) Directory: PMSDATA: c) TAS in processing: Y d) Vel threshold (clicks) 0 e) Calibration file: <i>Use the most recent calibration file.</i> Format FFSSP_CALddmmyyyy.txt Calibration files to be stored in MRFB:[PMS.FAST_FFSSP] f) Adjust FFSSP time Y/N g) If Y, enter value to add to data time (seconds)		Total glitches = Sec file written ok? Note calibration file used Yes only if gross errors occur in FFSSP time eg; ~ 1hour
5) FLOODS> WAVE a) WAVE> write_procffssp_to_m5,'pmsdata:Bnnn_procffssp.dat', 'mfddata:Bnnn_mfdX','pmsdata:Bnnn_m5procffssp',/auto b) WAVE> exit		Use PVWAVE for this section Note time correction applied to FFSSP by /auto =
6) FLOODS> MODIFY a) Modifying datasets: pmsdata:Bnnn_m5procffssp b) Dataset: mfddata:Bnnn_mfdX c) New dataset: mfddata:Bnnn_mfdY (y=x+1) d) Parameter description file: <i>leave blank to use default</i>		Input file size = M5 output file size =
7) CHECKS: i). Are FFSSP and JW/Nevzorov LWC synchronized in time? <i>In flight_plot, parameters</i> <i>JW LWC para 535</i> <i>Nevzorov LWC para 602</i> <i>FFSSP LWC para 1202</i> ii). If not, repeat from step 5b replacing /auto with addt=x which adds x+20 secs to FFSSP time.		Synchronized?

CORE-CLOUD-PHY_ to converted files		
9) FLOODS> RUN MRFB:[PMS.SPEC2D.AUTO]PROCESS2D_AUTO	yes	NB. an error message may appear, floating point exception, rerun and use time quoted in error message, repeat until successful. X = A
a) Flight number: Bnnn b) Directory: PMSDATA: c) File generation: <i>Hit enter</i> d) Time correction: <i>Time offset of the 2D data</i> e) TAS: Y f) MFD directory: MFDDATA:Bnnn_MFDX g) Probe number: (1) 2DC (2) 2DP (0) Both <i>0 unless either probe known to be faulty</i> h) Start time: <i>0 if unknown (T/O + 30sec)</i> i) End time: <i>240000 if unknown (Land – 30sec)</i> j) Nominal averaging: 0.2 seconds for conversion to M5 k) Particle type 2DC: 8 if known to be in ice cloud 11 if known to be in water cloud l) Particle type 2DP: 8 if known to be in mixed-phase 8 if unknown m) Coefficient choice: 2 n) Output root filename: PMSDATA:Bnnn_PROC2D	-1.5sec	Start = 092600 End = 131430 Time data processed to = 131332 2dproc files present *.2dc, *.2dp and *.dat
10) FLOODS> WAVE	yes	Use PVWAVE for this section
i) WAVE> WRITE_PROC2D_TO_M5, 'PMSDATA:BNNN_PROC2D.DAT', 'PMSDATA:BNNN_M5PROC2D' ii). exit		Error message about HDDR file should be ignored. Records =
11) FLOODS> MODIFY	yes	
a) Modifying datasets: pmsdata:Bnnn_m5proc2D b) Datset: mfddata:Bnnn_mfdX c) New dataset: mfddata:Bnnn_mfdY d) Parameter description file: leave blank to use default		MFDB
12) CHECKS:		
Are 2DC/2DP IWC of comparable magnitude and well-correlated with Nevzorov TWC? <i>In flight_plot, parameters</i> <i>Nevzerov TWC para 605</i> <i>2DC IWC para 1302</i> <i>2DP IWC para 1312</i>		No correlation at all

CLOUD PHYSICS PROCESSING LOG

Flight number: B305 **T/O:** 09:26:17
Date of flight: 11/07/07 **Land:** 13:14:30

C) PCASP PROCESSING		
Processing Stage	Done?	Comments
1) Complete stage 7) in 2D processing Ensures Bnnn_FSP.DAT containing raw PCASP data is written to directory PMSDATA:	Yes	
2) FLOODS> RUN MRFB:[PMS.PCASP]PROCPCASP_NEW a) Flight number: Bnnn b) File name: PMSDATA:Bnnn_FSP.DAT c) Root output name: PMSDATA:Bnnn_PROCPCASP Produces PMSDATA:Bnnn_PROCPCASP.DAT (binary) PMSDATA:Bnnn_PROCPCASP.OUT (ascii) d) Minimum size channel: <i>default = 1</i> <i>If smallest size channel are known to be noisy the value of the highest noise free channel to be entered here</i> e) Calibration volume flow rate: <i>Use the most recent value. 1.8ccs⁻¹</i> <i>Calibration files to be stored in Exeter</i> <i>Entering zero gives default value = 1.0 cm³s⁻¹</i> f) Time correction: <i>Same value as used in 2D processing stage 9d</i> g) Start time: <i>0 if unknown</i> h) End time: <i>240000 if unknown</i>		Min size = 1 Vol flow rate = 1.0
3) FLOODS> WAVE i). WAVE> write_procpcasp_to_m5, 'pmsdata:Bnnn_procpcasp.dat', 'pmsdata:Bnnn_m5procpcasp' ii). WAVE> exit	yes	Use PVWAVE for this section
4) FLOODS> MODIFY a) Modifying datasets: pmsdata:Bnnn_m5procpcasp b) Dataset: mfddata:Bnnn_mfdX c) New dataset: mfddata:Bnnn_mfdY d) Parameter description file: <i>leave blank to use default</i>	yes	MFDC
5) CHECKS Are PCASP and JW peaks synchronous? <i>In flight_plot, parameters</i> <i>JW LWC para 535</i> <i>PCASP conc para 1550</i>	yes	

CVI log B305

7/11/07 8:28:59 AM
7/11/07 8:29:44 AM
7/11/07 9:38:35 AM Not able to set CVI yet as in and out of cu2
7/11/07 9:38:57 AM Start of run 1.1
7/11/07 9:39:23 AM In aerosol mode
7/11/07 9:49:36 AM end of run 1.1
7/11/07 9:51:32 AM start of run 1.2
7/11/07 10:00:33 AM end of run 1.2
7/11/07 10:11:04 AM unable to get N opc count to settle at <1 (getting anything from 3 to 180!)
7/11/07 10:18:56 AM Have set up CVI mode following instructions explicitly in absence of being able to set it any other way - L Control set at 2.8
7/11/07 10:23:20 AM Temp out of CVI mode
7/11/07 10:40:42 AM Unable to get any sensible readings from CVI mode
7/11/07 10:42:33 AM flow light out on 3010 - not uncommon at this altitude
7/11/07 10:49:21 AM start of run 2.1
7/11/07 10:51:13 AM will remain in aerosol mode for rest of flight
7/11/07 10:52:17 AM end of run 2.1
7/11/07 10:56:26 AM start of run 3.1
7/11/07 11:01:18 AM end of run 3.1
7/11/07 11:03:23 AM start of run 4.1
7/11/07 11:04:12 AM real start of run 4.1
7/11/07 11:12:18 AM end of run 4.1 start of run 4.2
7/11/07 11:14:08 AM end of run 4.2
7/11/07 11:14:57 AM start of run 4.3
7/11/07 11:17:15 AM end of run 4.3
7/11/07 11:20:52 AM start of run 4.4
7/11/07 11:23:42 AM end of run 4.4
7/11/07 11:27:00 AM start of run 4.5
7/11/07 11:29:25 AM end of run 4.5
7/11/07 11:31:03 AM trying out cvi mode once more
7/11/07 11:33:12 AM start of run 4.6
7/11/07 11:35:02 AM end of run 4.6
7/11/07 11:35:21 AM continuing in cvi mode for now
7/11/07 11:37:54 AM start of run 4.7
7/11/07 11:56:51 AM start of run 5.1
7/11/07 11:58:08 AM end of run 5.1
7/11/07 12:01:40 PM start of run 5.2
7/11/07 12:02:49 PM start of run 6.1
7/11/07 12:04:28 PM end of run 6.1
7/11/07 12:07:41 PM start of run 6.2
7/11/07 12:11:06 PM end of run 6.2
7/11/07 12:14:01 PM start of run 6.3
7/11/07 12:15:46 PM end of run 6.3
7/11/07 12:18:14 PM start of run 6.4
7/11/07 12:19:28 PM end of run 6.4
7/11/07 12:22:46 PM start of run 6.5
7/11/07 12:25:05 PM end of run 6.5

Flight:

B305

KEY

- Duff Data
- Minor Problems
- OK
- Not Fitted
- Fitted, Not Operated

Thermometers

- Cabin Temperature:
- Heimann:
- Deiced Temp:
- Non-deiced Temp:

Hygrometers

- FWVS:
- General Eastern:
- Johnson Williams:
- Nevzorov:
- Total Water Probe:

Cameras

- Downward Facing:
- Forward Facing:
- Rearward Facing:
- Upward Facing:

Navigation + Aircraft

- Cruciform GPS:
- GIN Applanix:
- INU Honeywell:
- Radar Altimeter:
- RVSM IAS:
- RVSM Static Pressure:
- XR5 GPS:

Report Created 20/08/2007
17:25:51

Misc Core

- AMTG:
- AVAPS:
- Cabin Pressure:
- Fax machine:
- Printer:
- S9 Static Pressure:
- Satcom C:
- Satcom H:
- Turb Centre-Static:
- Turb Left Right:
- Turb Up-Down:
- Turb Horizontal Chk:
- Turb Vertical Chk:
- Weather Radar:
- DLUs:**
- DLU AERACK:
- DLU BBR Lower:
- DLU BBR Upper:
- DLU Core Chem:
- DLU Core Consoles:
- DLU Port Aft:
- DLU Port Fwd:
- DLU Stbd Fwd:

Radiometers

- Lower:**
- BBR (clear) Lower:
- BBR (IR) Lower:
- BBR (red) Lower:
- Upper:**
- BBR (clear) Upper:
- BBR (IR) Upper:
- BBR (red) Upper:
- ARIES:
- DEIMOS:
- IR Camera:
- JNO2 Lower:
- JNO2 Upper:
- JO1D Lower:
- JO1D Upper:
- MARSS:
- SHIMS Lower:
- SHIMS Upper:
- SWS:
- TAFTS:

Last Updated:

Cloud Probes

- 2DC:
- 2DP:
- FFSSP:
- PCASP:
- ADA:
- CCN:
- CDP:
- CIP 100:
- CIP 25:
- CPI:
- CVI:
- SID1:
- SID2:
- Aerosol**
- CPC 3025A:
- Filters 47mm:
- Filters 90mm:
- Neph - Dry:
- Neph - Wet:
- PSAP:
- AMS:
- CPC 3025 (AMS):
- INC:
- VACC:
- CPC 3010A (CVI):

01/08/2007 12:06:15

Chemistry

- CO Aerolaser 5002:
- NOx TE42C:
- Ozone TE49C:
- Ozone TE49:
- SO2 TE43C:
- TDLAS (NIR) CH4:
- TDLAS (NIR) CO2:
- FAGE:
- Formaldehyde:
- NOxy:
- ORAC:
- PAN:
- PERCA:
- Peroxide:
- PTRMS:
- TDLAS (1C):
- WAS Bags:
- WAS Bottles:
- Misc Non-Core**
- CASI/ATM:
- LIDAR:
- LTI:
- SAW Hygrometer:

Pre-Flighter's Log

Date: 11/07/07

Flight No: B306

Pre-Flighter: Bob Wells

<u>No.</u>	<u>✓ or x</u>	<u>Location</u>	<u>Action</u>	<u>Comments</u>
1	<input type="checkbox"/>	Hangar	Collect Dustbin, put on a/c	
<u>Aircraft Cabin: Power-up</u>				
2	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Core Chemistry	Gases x 3 ON	
3	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Cabin	All Racks Checked	
4	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Fwd CorCon	All reqd CBs made	
5	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Aft CorCon	CBs made, PCs ON	
6	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	HORACE	Optical Disk loaded	
7	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	HORACE	Recording data	
8	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	HORACE	DLU Status Checked	
9	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	HORACE	HORACE Status Checked	
10	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Satcom H	Power LED ON	
11	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Nevzorov	Checked and OFF	
12	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	GPS	Checked	
13	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	INU	Align	
14	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Cameras Pictures	Checked x 4 OK	
15	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Core Chemistry	Instruments Checked OK	
16	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Core Chemistry	CO Flows Checked OK	Cal Cell p 5:17
17	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	FWVS	Set up	
18	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Video x 2	Records okay, Rewind	
19	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Delced Rosemount	Heater Checked / Set	
20	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Heimann	Calibration Checked	
21	<input type="checkbox"/>	TWC	ON & Checked	Not checked
22	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	GE	Balance checked	
23	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	INU	Navigate then back to Align	
24	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Hubs x 4	Checked ON	
25	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Fwd Console	Miss. Sci Laptop CB made	& CB on Port Fwd SSP
26	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	CNC	Butanol filled	
27	<input type="checkbox"/>	Dry Neph	Power up & Zero Cal	No cal
28	<input type="checkbox"/>	CGPS	Set up	
29	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Miss. Sci Laptop	Checked Onboard	
Proceed to External Checks				
	<input type="checkbox"/>			
	<input type="checkbox"/>			
	<input type="checkbox"/>			

External Checks overleaf

Pre-Flighter's Log

<u>No.</u>	<u>√ or x</u>	<u>Location</u>	<u>Action</u>	<u>Comments</u>
<u>External Checks</u>				
29	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Turb Probe	Clean if reqd, Photo taken	
30	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	JW	Cleaned & Checked	
31	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	DI Rosemount	Cleaned & Checked	
32	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	NDI Rosemount	Cleaned & Checked	
33	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Nevzorov	Cleaned/windings checked	
34	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	GE	Cleaned & Checked	
35	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Lower BBRs	Domes cleaned/checked	
36	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Camera Windows	Cleaned	
37	<input type="checkbox"/>	Heimann	Lens checked OK	
38	<input type="checkbox"/>	TWC Cover	Fitted if required	
39	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	All other covers	Removed	
40	<input type="checkbox"/>	Dustbin	Returned to hangar	
41	<input type="checkbox"/>	Tools	Check ALL in Toolkit	
42	<input type="checkbox"/>	Tools	Avalon informed	
<u>Avalon Checks</u>				Signed
43	<input type="checkbox"/>	Upper BBRs Checked & Cleaned		
44	<input type="checkbox"/>	ICEX applied		
45	<input type="checkbox"/>	Turb Probe - Traps emptied, detail contents -		a)Nil b)1-2 drops c)1/4 full or more
46	<input type="checkbox"/>	Turb Probe - Traps dried and resealed		

MISSING LOG SHEETS:

The following log sheets are not available for flight B305:

Log	Reason
Flight Manager's Faults/Incidents log	No log was created at the time and will not be created now.
Core Chemistry	no In Flight log except in cases of instrument problems
VACC	VACC operator does not create a log sheet
PSAP log	No log as PSAP pump/filter info included on Flight Summary page
CPI	CPI operator does not create a log sheet

Document control

Revision	Date	Author	Comments
r0	02 Oct 2007	Doug Anderson	Initial version missing the above noted logs
r1	15 Jan 2008	Doug Anderson	Updated video tape holder information
r2			

VIDEO RECORDINGS:

2 x Rearward Facing Cameras

3 x Forward Facing Cameras

Digital8 video recordings from this flight reside with :

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